

Echocardiogram: A Tool to Diagnose Emphysematous Pyelonephritis?! An interesting case

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ABSTRACT

We present for the first time in the literature a 79-year-old patient with stage 4 chronic kidney disease and other comorbidities, who was admitted to the Nephrology Department complaining for weakness and fatigue. After positive blood cultures for *Streptococcus gallolyticus* development, an echocardiogram was performed searching the source of infection, that revealed air bubbles in right chambers, inferior vena cava and hepatic veins. A suspicion of emphysematous pyelonephritis was raised after that echo finding, and that was the diagnosis which a Computed Tomography of the abdomen and pelvis finally set. The patient was managed with broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy and a drainage using double-J ureteral catheter.

Keywords: Echocardiogram, Emphysematous pyelonephritis, *Streptococcus gallolyticus*

CASE REPORT

A 79-year-old patient with a history of coronary artery disease with previous angioplasty, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, insulin-dependent diabetes with poor glycaemic control, and chronic kidney disease stage 4, presented to the emergency department (ED) complaining of weakness and fatigue, loss of appetite that had been progressively worsening over the past three days. The patient had referred a recent revision of the arteriovenous fistula in the left upper limb due to signs of steal syndrome (jump graft). At ED, the patient was haemodynamically stable with peripheral oedemas and positive hepatojugular sign, while nothing else was remarkable during the initial physical examination. Laboratory tests revealed normal amounts of leukocytes and platelets. However, the results indicated microcytic hypochromic anaemia (Hgb: 8.5 g/dL), impaired renal function (Creatinine: 3.51 mg/dL), elevated potassium (K: 5.8 mmol/L) and increased inflammatory biomarkers (CRP: 24 mg/L, normal values <5mg/dL). The chest X-ray was normal, while the electrocardiogram showed sinus rhythm without ischemic changes. Therefore, the patient was admitted to the Department of Nephrology for further investigation.

During his hospitalization, urine cultures were taken. The first culture showed mixed growth, while the second culture (taken after the catheter was changed) revealed *Streptococcus gallolyticus* (Sg), previously known as

Streptococcus bovis, a Gram-positive group D Streptococcus, that is considered an opportunistic pathogen. An ultrasound (US) of the kidneys, ureters, and bladder was performed, revealing increased echogenicity of the kidneys with almost complete loss of corticomedullary differentiation, consistent with chronic kidney disease. Additionally, the left kidney showed significant dilation of the pelvicalyceal system without evidence of a stone. It also revealed a small to moderate amount of free fluid collection in the abdomen and pelvis, a moderate pleural effusion bilaterally, and a suspicion of a small pericardial effusion. For that reason, an echocardiogram was performed, which showed air bubbles in right chambers, inferior vena cava and hepatic veins ([Image 1](#), [Image 2](#), [Video 1](#) and [Video 2](#)). Subsequently, the patient underwent a computed tomography (CT) of the abdomen and pelvis, which confirmed the significant dilation of the left pelvicalyceal system with an extrarenal pelvis and numerous extensive air bubbles in the renal tissue, consistent with emphysematous pyelonephritis (EPN), without evidence of a stone.

Once the diagnosis of EPN was established, the patient was placed on intravenous broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy (meropenem and metronidazole). Immediate urological evaluation was conducted, and a drainage using double-J ureteral catheter in the left kidney was performed.

Image 1: TTE Subcoastal 4C view

Image 2: TTE Subcoastal IVC-RA focused view.

DISCUSSION

EPN is a life-threatening necrotizing kidney infection, with limited case series documented in the literature. The primary causative organisms are *Escherichia coli*, followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and Group D streptococcus.^[1] The mixed acid fermentation of glucose by Enterobacteriaceae is the major pathway of gas formation.^[2] Diabetes mellitus (DM) is the most common predisposing factor, along with poor tissue perfusion, the presence of urinary tract infection, and decreased host immunity.^[1,3,4] It is worth noting that diabetic patients with EPN have an increased risk of complications compared to those with simple pyelonephritis.^[3]

Diagnosis typically requires a high level of suspicion, with CT of kidneys, ureters, and bladder being the preferred diagnostic tool. According to the radiological findings on CT scans, EPN is classified into the following categories:^[2]

1. **Class 1:** Gas is present only in the collecting system.
2. **Class 2:** Gas is located in the renal parenchyma without extending to the extrarenal space.
3. **Class 3A:** Gas or abscess extends to the perirenal space.
4. **Class 3B:** Gas or abscess extends to the pararenal space.
5. **Class 4:** Bilateral EPN or EPN in a solitary kidney.

Gas extension into the great vessels is not included in this classification. However, the gas can slowly resolve into the stream passing through the anterior renal fascia (Gerota's fascia) and the posterior renal fascia (Zuckerkandl's fascia).^[5] The presence of air in the inferior vena cava can either be asymptomatic or cause sudden cardiorespiratory collapse, requiring immediate intervention.^[1] The management of EPN involves broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy and percutaneous drainage through bilateral nephrostomies. In severe cases with poor response to previous management, hemodynamic instability and extensive necrosis in the kidneys, surgical intervention with partial or total nephrectomy may be necessary.^[2,6]

Our case report is unique in the literature, documenting the presence of air bubbles in the right chambers of the heart in a patient with EPN. The initial detection of them through an echocardiogram prompted inquiries into their origin. Initially, we considered that air bubbles might be coming from the patient's AVF fistula. However, this hypothesis was dismissed because air from such a source would typically be expected in the superior vena cava rather than the inferior vena cava. Following this line of reasoning, a CT scan of the abdomen and pelvis was conducted, revealing the presence of EPN. This diagnosis raised further questions about the connection between the EPN and the presence of air in the right heart chambers.

The kidney eliminates its contents through both the venous and lymphatic systems. Lymphatic drainage proceeds through its system, culminating in the major (left) and minor (right) thoracic duct, positioned at the junction of the subclavian and jugular veins. From there, the lymph enters the venous system and eventually reaches the superior vena cava. Therefore, the possibility that the air bubbles originated from the lymphatic system was rejected.^[7]

Upon reviewing the literature, we found several case reports discussing the association between EPN and the presence of gas in the venous circulation. A potential explanation could be attributed to the pressure gradient.

The intrarenal pressure is expected to be elevated due to the accumulation of gas, released by the gas-forming bacteria. Therefore, this increased pressure can force gas into the low-pressure venous system, allowing it to travel through the renal veins into the inferior vena cava.^[1] In severe cases of EPN, it has also been described the hypothesis that the infection can disrupt renal tissue, including the wall of the renal veins. Hence, this destruction can create a direct pathway for gas to enter the venous circulation.^[8] In any case, once the gas enters the inferior vena cava, it can travel to the right side of the heart and potentially into the pulmonary circulation, leading to air embolism.^[6]

Fortunately, our patient, despite the presence of air in the inferior vena cava and its extension into the right chambers of the heart, did not exhibit symptoms or signs of hemodynamic instability and had a good response to intravenous antibiotic therapy and drainage using a double-J ureteral catheter in the left kidney.

The patient provided written informed consent for the publication of the case history and the use of radiological and echocardiographic images. All patient identifiers were removed from the case report and images to ensure confidentiality.

REFERENCES

1. [Sharma N, Quarrier S. Emphysematous pyelonephritis developing in the contralateral kidney following ureteroscopy: An unusual presentation. Urol Case Rep. 2022;43:102086.](#)
2. [Huang JJ, Tseng CC. Emphysematous pyelonephritis: clinicoradiological classification, management, prognosis, and pathogenesis. Arch Intern Med. 2000;160\(6\):797-805.](#)
3. [Nabi T, Rafiq N, Rahman MHU, Rasool S, Wani NUD. Comparative study of emphysematous pyelonephritis and pyelonephritis in type 2 diabetes: a single-centre experience. J Diabetes Metab Disord. 2020;19\(2\):1273-82.](#)
4. [Harsch IA, Langer K, Abramowski C, Konturek PC. Emphysematous pyelonephritis - a rare complication of diabetes mellitus. Wiad Lek. 2018;71\(4\):917-21.](#)
5. [Chesbrough RM, Burkhard TK, Martinez AJ, Burks DD. Gerota versus Zuckerkandl: the renal fascia revisited. Radiology. 1989;173\(3\):845-6.](#)
6. [Perkins TA, Rogman A, Ankem MK. Emphysematous pyelonephritis with air bubble in the inferior vena cava. African Journal of Urology. 2020;26\(1\):69.](#)
7. [Russell PS, Hong J, Windsor JA, Itkin M, Phillips ARJ. Renal Lymphatics: Anatomy, Physiology, and Clinical Implications. Front Physiol. 2019;10:251.](#)
8. [Jimenez-Castillo RA, Carrizales-Sepulveda EF, Obeso-Fernandez J, Vera-Pineda R, Nanez-Terrerros H. Presence of air in the inferior vena cava: an uncommon radiologic presentation of emphysematous pyelonephritis. Intern Emerg Med. 2020;15\(1\):149-50.](#)